

Playing the role of the nurse as a patient

supporter in hypertensive patients in the emergency department: providing a theoretical model

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Desempeñando el papel del enfermero como soporte del paciente en pacientes hipertensos en el servicio de urgencias: aportando un modelo teórico

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Abstract

Introduction & Background: The primary mission of healthcare providers is to preserve life and provide comfort. The comfort of patients referring to the emergency department is undeniable. Since emergency departments receive patients with internal ailments such as diabetic ketoacidosis, hypertension, chemical poisoning, and multiple systemic traumas. The emergency department nurse is required to play the role of advocate for these patients at higher risk. The primary goal of this study was to explain the process of playing the role of patient advocacy.

Methods: This study was conducted qualitatively and using the grounded theory method. Seventeen nurses working in the emergency department from 4 selected hospitals of Gilan University of Medical Sciences based on the primary emergency centers in Rasht city were included in the study purposefully and using a theoretical sampling method. Data were collected with semi-structured interviews and indirect observation. Data were analyzed simultaneously using the Strauss and Corbin approach. At first, Maxq-d-19 software was used to organize the data.

Results: In the data analysis, two primary categories of condition complexity and prudent comprehensive care were identified with 6 and 3 subcategories, respectively. Playing the role of a nurse in patient advocacy in the emergency department is a dynamic and repetitive process. The combined concept of “work creation and prudent care of a comfortable life” was the clearest concept revealed in the data. It was the most abstract concept that covered all the concepts. The complicated conditions of the emergency department are the primary barrier to playing the role of nurse advocacy in the emergency department.

Conclusion: In emergency department conditions, it is necessary to provide the conditions for the realization of the concept of the role of the nurse as the patient’s advocate with work creation and comprehensive care of life and comfort. Fundamental legislation in the health system seems necessary in playing the role of the nurse as a patient advocate.

Keywords: Nurse, Patient advocacy, Emergency, Grounded Theory, Corbin Strauss.

Introducción y antecedentes. La misión principal de los proveedores de atención médica es preservar la vida y brindar comodidad. El cumplimiento de esta misión es más prominente en los departamentos de emergencia y enfermedades agudas como la presión arterial. La comodidad de los pacientes de emergencia es innegable. La enfermera de urgencias está obligada a desempeñar el papel de defensora de estos pacientes de mayor riesgo para reducir las complicaciones de la enfermedad. El objetivo principal de este estudio fue explicar el proceso de desempeñar el papel de apoyo al paciente.

Métodos. Este estudio se realizó de forma cualitativa y utilizando el método de la teoría fundamentada. Diecisiete enfermeras que trabajan en el departamento de emergencias de 4 hospitales seleccionados de la Universidad de Ciencias Médicas de Gilan con base en los centros primarios de emergencia en la ciudad de Rasht se incluyeron en el estudio a propósito y utilizando un método de muestreo teórico. Los datos fueron recolectados con entrevistas semiestructuradas y observación indirecta. Los datos se analizaron simultáneamente utilizando el enfoque de Strauss y Corbin. Al principio, se utilizó el software Maxqd-19 para organizar los datos.

Resultados. En el análisis de datos, se identificaron dos categorías principales de complejidad de la condición y atención integral prudente con 6 y 3 subcategorías, respectivamente. Desempeñar el papel de una enfermera en el apoyo a los pacientes con presión arterial alta en el servicio de urgencias es un proceso dinámico y repetitivo. El concepto combinado de “crear trabajo y cuidar prudentemente de una vida cómoda” fue el concepto más claro revelado en los datos. Era el concepto más abstracto que abarcaba todos los conceptos. La compleja condición del servicio de urgencias es el principal obstáculo para desempeñar el papel de apoyo de la enfermera en el servicio de urgencias, cuya mejora redundará en la reducción de las complicaciones de la hipertensión.

Conclusión. En situaciones de emergencia, es necesario proporcionar las condiciones para la realización del concepto del papel del enfermero como soporte del paciente mediante la creación de trabajo y cuidado integral de la vida y la comodidad. Parece necesaria una legislación básica en el sistema de salud al desempeñar el papel de la enfermera como sostén del paciente, el color completo de este papel es más evidente en la recuperación y reducción de las complicaciones de enfermedades agudas y peligrosas como la hipertensión arterial.

Palabras clave: Enfermera, Defensa del paciente, Hipertensión, Emergencia, Teoría fundamentada, Corbin Strauss.

Over the last decades, there have been many ethical challenges in this field given the progress of treatment. The nurses have been required to play roles such as accountability, caring, advocating, training, and management¹. Patient safety and advocacy is a serious global challenge and a crucial dimension of healthcare quality. Ensuring patient safety and providing safe care should be considered by health providers as the first critical step in providing health care². Patient safety means “preventing harm to patients while receiving health services”³. The World Health Organization has declared patient safety a serious public health concern⁴. In maintaining patient safety and advocacy, the competence of human resources, especially nurses, has a particular significance as the front line of the health system⁵. Since nurses are the largest part of the professional forces of the health system, it is very crucial to pay attention to the competence of nurses in the field of patient safety and advocacy⁶. Due to its unpredictable nature and high staff turnover, the emergency department is a special and unique work environment for nurses, and factors such as heavy work and lack of time and manpower in the emergency department affect the way of providing care in this department⁷. The majority of hospital visits belong to the emergency department, and the emergency nurse is the first person from the hospital’s care workers who meets them at this point⁸. Compared to the past, emergency nurses are more specialized in dealing with acute diseases such as high blood pressure⁹.

The emergency nurse should be aware of the policies of the health system. Generally, the emergency nurse is the patient’s advocate and protects his or her safety^{8,10}. Emergency department staff, especially nurses should try to play multiple roles (care provider, researcher, consultant, and advocate) in a completely unpredictable situation¹¹. Generally, it can be stated that the emergency department is unpredictable, crowded, and lacks human resources with low management support⁷. Its employees, especially nurses, should be patient advocates in such a special field, in addition to the need to be aware of the policies of the health system¹⁰. The real meaning of care for emergency nurses is playing the role of a nurse as a patient advocate and providing comprehensive care for him or her⁷. Nurses’ perceptions and positive attitudes toward their role are driving forces for the emergence of patient advocacy behavior in them. Nurses play a significant role in opening communication channels between patients and physicians or other nurses, in such a way that they pursue and examine all patient complaints; whether they are simple or complex. The question is what is the role of the nurse in the emergency department in patient advocacy¹².

Jabari showed a significant and direct relationship between the professional behavior of nurses and the safety culture of acute and emergency patients such as hypertension patients. He showed that by increasing the professional behavior of nurses, the culture of patient safety improves¹³. The assistant examined the role of the nurse's safety and showed that the presence of the nurse is a factor in feeling psychological security, the presence of the nurse is a factor in receiving the necessary information, and the presence of the nurse is a factor in recognizing and being timely, and this recognition can be the key to reducing the complications of hypertension and quick recovery. You will be more sick. The results of this study increase patients' awareness of safety and support nurses. The results of this study increase the awareness of nurses in dealing with the needs of patients with high blood pressure. He also showed that nursing managers and educators will be able to design and implement their management and educational activities based on insights based on scientific and ethical findings in such a way that the necessary conditions for the compassionate presence of students and nurses are provided¹⁴. Considering the importance of the subject, the present research is an attempt to explain the process of the nurse's role in supporting acute hypertension patients in the emergency room and finally presenting a theoretical model in eight hospitals of Gilan University of Medical Sciences (Porsina, Razi, Heshmat and Shafa) in Rasht.

from the eight hospitals of Gilan University of Medical Sciences (Poorsina, Razi, Heshmat, and Shafa) in Rasht city were included in the study using purposeful sampling and then theoretical sampling. Data were collected using semi-structured interviews and observation. The information was analyzed using 5 stages of concept identification, development of concepts according to characteristics and dimensions, analysis for the context, entering the process into the analysis, and combination of classes according to the Strauss & Corbin (2014) approach¹. Maxqd-19 software was first used to organize the data. The primary tool to collect data in this study was the researcher. The method of data collection was the semi-structured interview and indirect observation, daily notes, documents, and scientific texts. The word software was used to record data. By considering the data, primary codes, primary classes, sub-classes, and primary concepts emerged.

The first familiarization session was held via phone or in person. Then, the researcher introduced himself and stated the study objectives and details of the study. Then, the subjects were invited to participate in the study and conduct an interview. After the nurse verbally agreed to participate in the study and after obtaining informed consent, the time and place of the interview were determined with the agreement of the participants. Then, they completed the informed consent form. At the beginning of each interview, the researcher introduced himself and explained the study objectives to the participants. Before conducting each interview, by asking questions related to the demographic characteristics of the participants and establishing proper communication, and gaining their trust (introducing the researcher as an experienced faculty instructor with theoretical, practical, and clinical teaching), he provided the conditions for a better and easier interview to guide the flow of the interview to achieve the goal.

Interviews were semi-structured. They started with a general and open-ended question: "Please tell me about your patient advocacy experience". Given what was stated and by asking clarifying questions, the researcher tried to make the content of each interview cover the goal of the study. An interview guide was used to keep the questions related to the goal of the study, guide the study correctly, and extract the facts, mindsets, processes, and views of the participants. The interview guide included open-ended questions that allowed the participants to express their views and experiences. An attempt was made to maintain an open interview technique during the interview process despite the use of an interview guide. Then, the interviews were transcribed word by word and typed into Word 2013 software. Then, the Word file of each interview was entered into the MAXQDA-19 software, which took about a month. Then, it was micro-analyzed as a manuscript. The data were analyzed based on 5 overlapping stages (microanalysis, conceptualization, entering the process, entering the result, and integrating the variables).

The present study was conducted using the grounded theory method. This method's special feature is to generate a theory from the data and simultaneously a collection of data and their analysis. Grounded theory is one of the qualitative research methods that aim at developing the theory. Grounded theory starts with a research situation without a hypothesis, and the researcher starts his work with his favorite subject and collects data, and allows related ideas to develop and expand. First, beliefs are derived inductively from the data and form a mini-theory, which may be confirmed or rejected by theoretical sampling¹. Grounded theory is searching for processes in the social context and when the goal is to develop a theory to explain human behavior; grounded theory will be a suitable approach for research.

Since nursing is related to human behavior, this approach can be used in nursing research. Seventeen emergency department nurses from 4 public hospitals

Data collection and analysis:

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews by researchers from nurses working in the emergency department of the hospital. The interview guide was designed by the study researchers to help collect appropriate and in-depth information from the study participants. The researcher reviewed and re-read the text of the audio files several times to get a general understanding of the concepts inside them. To identify the key sentences and concepts in the interviews, the text of the interviews was checked line by line and word by word, and a code was given to each sentence or keyword. The codes were named based on the participants' own words or the researcher's inference. After open coding, the codes were classified and primary codes were extracted. Then, the classes were placed in more abstract classes based on their characteristics and dimensions. At this stage, the researcher compared the codes and primary classes that emerged during the open coding stage with each other regarding the similarities and differences and combined the codes that were conceptually similar to each other. The content of the classes that were related to each other was placed around a common axis and identified with a name that indicated the content of each class.

In analyzing the data for the context, various factors were identified. Table 1 shows the formation of the primary class of the complexity of the emergency department:

Primary category	Sub-category	Primary class
Complicated conditions of emergency department	workload	Multiplicity of clinical tasks
		Multiplicity of non-clinical tasks (writing, etc.)
	Wrong organizational culture	Gender-based treatment
		discrimination
		Doctor dominance/medical professional dominance
		Wrong modeling
	wrong manners	wrong manner of visiting
		wrong manner of report writing
	inappropriate management structure	Inappropriate delegation of power
		selecting an incompetent official
	Shortages	Lack of facilities
		Lack of efficient human resources
	Inappropriate physical environment	Inappropriate triage structure
		Inappropriate structure of the department
		Noise
		Turnover/overflow

After the first and second interviews, the researcher guided the subsequent interviews based on the concepts extracted from the previous interview. The researcher

questioned the use of analytical tools during the analysis and the resulting concepts in terms of their characteristics and dimensions. He asked different questions in different situations and then looked for their answers in the findings. If he did not get enough answers, he followed them with a more sensitive mind in the next interviews, so no case was left unnoticed or ambiguous. The use of "Situational communication guide" and "reflection coding" matrices helped to specify the conditions, strategies, and implications.

Results

Table 2 presents the demographic characteristics of the participants.

Regarding their education, 12 people had bachelor's (70.6%) and 5 had master's (29.4%) degrees. Eight of them (47%) were married and 9 (53%) were single. Eight of them had an official (47%), 3 had contractual (17.7%) and 6 had project-based (35.3%) employment status.

Characteristics of the nurse advocate

According to the performed interviews, the characteristics of the nurse advocate include self-sacrifice, patience, being experienced, being up-to-date, risk-taking, professional commitment, intrinsic motivation, persistence in work, resiliency, spiritual helper, empowerment of self and others, work creation, clinical competence (scientific and practical), clinical judgment, clinical inquiry, the ability to participate, life philosophy, and reverence of life.

Characteristics of patients who need nurse advocacy

Data were analyzed regarding patient characteristics. "Unpredictable and special changing life situations (elderly, child, unconscious, woman, prisoner, Trans, and socially abandoned) of patients referring to the emergency department was one of the characteristics of the patient who needs the nurse's advocacy in the emergency department.

Attention to processes in data analysis:

The nurse prioritizes, participates, monitors, directs, and refers under the title of management care behavior, and gives encouragement and even false hope under the title of psychological care behavior. He or she also performs routine and non-routine clinical tasks under the title of care behavior and plays the role of advocacy in the continuum of preserving life to comfort (based on the chang-

ing status of the emergency patient from red to green). The analysis of the generated data revealed the success of nurse advocacy in the complicated conditions of the emergency department (Table 3).

«Work creation and comprehensive care” is the primary approach and class that emerged after analyzing the data. The result of open coding regarding bringing the process into the analysis was thirteen primary categories and eight subcategories (Table 3).

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of the research participants

Row	Age (year)	Education	Employment status	Job shift	Position	Marital status	Number of children	Employment history (year)	
								Emergency	Total
1	40	Bachelor	Contractual	Rotational	Nurse	Married	1	7	6
2	54	Master in anesthesia	Official	-	Educator	Single	-	22	26
3	26	Bachelor	Project-based	Rotational	Nurse B	Single	-	2	2
4	48	Bachelor	Official	Night	Shift officer	Single	-	22	22
5	40	Bachelor	Official	Morning	nurse	Single	-	13	13
6	38	Master	Contractual	Rotational	nurse	Married	-	8	10
7	42	Master in clinical psychology	Official	Morning	Head nurse	Married	2	4	10
8	25	Bachelor	Project-based	Rotational	nurse	Married	-	1	1
9	26	Bachelor	Project-based	Rotational	nurse	Single	-	1	1
10	26	Bachelor	Project-based	Rotational	nurse	Single	-	1	1
11	26	Bachelor	Project-based	Rotational	nurse	Single	-	2	2
12	26	Bachelor	Project-based	Rotational	nurse	Single	-	2	2
13	50	Master in management	Official	Morning	Head of department	Married	2	8	25
14	46	Bachelor	Official	Morning	Head nurse	Married	2	6	20
15	48	Master	Contractual	Rotational	Shift officer	Single	-	3	5
16	45	Bachelor	Official	Rotational	Shift officer	Married	-	13	20
17	46	Bachelor	Official	Rotational	Emergency supervisor	Married	-	14	21

Table 3. Themes and primary classes and subclasses classes related to the process

Primary class	subclasses	Primary classes	Primary codes
Prudent comprehensive care	Prudent care Attention to duty Useful work Prevention of damage and harm Prevention of conflict Providing comfort and convenience	Prioritizing	Prioritizing duties Preserving life Keeping calm Patient prioritization preserving life Keeping calm
		Participation	Work division preserving life Keeping calm
			Shift work. preserving life Keeping calm
			Participation
		Monitoring Attention to duty. Useful work - Prevention of damage and harm - Prevention of conflict	Monitoring Legal Physical-psychological preserving life Keeping calm
		Guidance/Management Attention to duty. Useful work Prevention of damage and harm Prevention of conflict	Guidance New co-worker Patient caregiver preserving life Keeping calm
	Referring	Referring Legal Psychological Social Preserving life Keeping calm	
	Psychological care Relaxing and calming Encouraging Giving hope, even a false one Providing comfort and convenience	calming Reducing tension Making the right decision Self-directing Acceleration of work Facilitation of work Prevention of damage and harm Useful work	Calming Reducing tension Making the right decision Self-directing Acceleration of work Facilitation of work Prevention of damage and harm Useful work Preserving life Keeping calm
		Being with the patient Reducing tension- Making the right decision Self-directing Acceleration of work Facilitation of work Prevention of damage and harm Useful work Preserving life Maintaining comfort	Encouraging Reducing tension Making the right decision Self-directing Acceleration of work Facilitation of work Prevention of damage and harm Preserving life Keeping calm
			Giving hope even unrealistic hope Reducing tension Making the right decision Self-directing Acceleration of work Facilitation of work Prevention of damage and harm Useful work Preserving life Keeping calm
Routine care	Routine care Attention to duty. Prevention of damage and harm Useful work	Routine clinical tasks Continuous clinical examination Performing clinical procedures Clinical handing over of the patient Clinical delivery of the patient	
		Routine non-clinical duties Delivering shifts at the nursing station Checking equipment and devices Working with HIS Secretary Handing over the shift at the nursing station	

Prudent comprehensive care of life-comfort

This primary category, which is the strategies of the nurse advocate, was the result of three sub-categories: “A: prudent care”, “B: psychological care” and C: routine care, which are discussed below.

Advocacy outcomes

At each stage of the analysis, the outcomes of the nurse’s advocacy of the patient were also considered. These outcomes were divided into two primary categories. The positive and negative outcomes of advocacy are for the nurse advocate and the successful and unsuccessful outcomes for the patient.

Simultaneous with continuous analytical comparison in the generation of complementary data, the central class and the primary concern of the participants is the prudent comprehensive care of life-comfort based on the vital condition of the patient (from red to green). This concept is the key concept of a combination of the concepts of prudent comprehensive work creation and prudent comprehensive life-comfort care in playing the role of emergency nurse advocate. This combined concept seems to guide all actions of the emergency nurse in playing the role of patient advocate in this department.

Analysis results:

- 1-The complexity of emergency conditions (workload, wrong organizational culture, wrong manners, inappropriate management structure, inappropriate physical structure, and shortage) has a relationship with playing the role of patient advocacy.
- 2-The emergency (from red to green) has a relationship with the nurse’s advocacy role.
- 3-The nurse’s characteristics have a relationship with his or her advocacy role.
- 4-The patient’s characteristics have a relationship with the playing the role of nurse advocacy.
- 5-The process of playing the role of nurse advocacy in the emergency department is dynamic.
- 6-The advocacy approach of the emergency nurse is work creation and the provision of prudent comprehensive care.
- 7-The outcome of a successful advocacy process for the emergency nurse is to preserve patient’s life and comfort.

The primary goal of the nurse is to preserve the patient’s life and comfort. The personal characteristics of the emergency nurse advocate are the factors that facilitate advocacy, and the complexity of the emergency department conditions prevents his or her advocacy role. The ambiguity of the legal status of nurse advocacy was evident from the beginning to the end of this study. In this

regard, there is a special group of patients who need to play the role of nurse advocacy. These patients include victims of child abuse, mentally-retarded, the elderly, especially the elderly with impaired senses, socially-abandoned people, and patients exposed to discrimination: women (domestic violence), and LGBTs.

The following points were considered in presenting the theoretical model (Figure 1):

In theorizing and presenting the model in nursing, four components of nursing, patient, health, and environment are considered.

- Nursing: Nursing is considered dynamic and prudent comprehensive care.
- Patient: a patient is a person whose life and well-being are in danger.
- Health: there is a risk of death and disrupting the patient’s well-being.
- Environment: emergency department, whose conditions are complicated

Figure 1. Proposed theoretical model: the process of playing a productive role of prudent comprehensive care

According to the results of this study, the primary concept revealed from the analysis of the data produced by the emergency nurse advocate is “prudent comprehensive work creation and care” in the continuum of triage, from red to green status, a dynamic process from preserving life to maintaining comfort. The data produced in this study revealed the term “reverence of life” which seems to be the horizon of the advocate nurse. The life-comfort prudent work creation of the nurse advocate is the result of accelerating and facilitating care with sobriety, politeness, respect, silence, courage, mediation, referral, and follow-up of affairs. Venki et al. referred to the nurse’s advocacy only in the physical area¹⁵. Dadvand et al. referred to the two primary themes of sympathy and protection of the nurse advocate¹⁶, which is consistent with the present study. Based on the present study, the most significant barrier to playing the role of an emergency nurse advocate is the complicated conditions of the emergency department; workload, wrong organizational culture, wrong manners, inappropriate management structure, inappropriate physical structure, and shortage were the subclasses of this primary class. At the macro level, these conditions prevent the nurse from playing the role of advocate.

Negarandeh et al. stated that the factors preventing the role of nurse advocacy are the lack of support for nurses and the absence of codes of ethics and the danger of advocacy for nurses¹⁷, which is in line with the present study. The characteristic of the nurse advocate becomes one of the facilitating factors in playing her role as an advocate. Data generation and analysis revealed sacrifice, patience, experience, being up-to-date, risk-taking, intrinsic motivation, persistence in work/resilience, spiritual belief, kinship, empowerment of self and others, work creation, scientific and practical competence, clinical judgment, ability to participate, and the reverence of life as the characteristics for the nurse advocate.

Moreover, the results of the analysis of the generated data were formed when bringing the process to the context of the primary classes of prioritization, participation, monitoring, mentoring, and referral. The characteristics of emergency patients that need advocacy were other factors that affect the start and continuation of this process. Negarandeh et al. declared that informing and training, valuing and respecting, providing physical, emotional, and financial support, and protecting and providing continuous care as the nurse advocacy for the patient¹⁷. The data of this study revealed that the primary goal of nurse advocacy is to preserve the life and comfort of the patient. Mortell et al. showed the goal of advocacy as a good human being¹⁸. The data showed that

nurse advocacy can cause him or her to be considered a nuisance by his or her coworkers. Bu and Jezowski also showed that nurse advocacy may be punished by coworkers and the organization¹⁹.

The data of this study revealed the variable, critical, and unpredictable conditions as the characteristics of the patient who needs advocacy. The proposed theoretical model is explanatory. The results of the present study revealed that preserving life and comfort is the primary concept that is responsible for the activity of the emergency nurse advocate. Based on the classic definition, patient advocacy means patient participation in care, informing the patient, and claiming the patient’s rights²⁰. However, the present study concluded that this definition includes only three approaches to achieving this role. To play this role, the nurse works dynamically between the bedside and the emergency department, and in the emergency department, playing this dynamic role is necessary to preserve the life and comfort of the patient. In case of success in the nurse’s advocacy, the inner satisfaction and freedom in the action will be achieved and the patient will survive or be in comfort.

Conclusions

Given the significant role of the nurse advocate in the emergency department, including “prudent comprehensive work and care in line with preserving life and comfort” and the main barrier to solving this concern, which is the “complicated nature of the emergency department”, it can be stated that by creating the appropriate conditions, the nurse will be able to quickly assess the patient’s life and comfort needs, intelligently plan and quickly implement effective measures so patients in the emergency department regain their health and recover by receiving care and treatment services. In this regard, it seems that fundamental legislation in the health system is necessary in playing the role of the nurse as a patient advocate.

Recommendations

The practical recommendations of the present study are as follows.

The results of the present study can be used by those involved in nursing education to take a step toward filling the gap between theory and clinical practice. The present study revealed that emergency nurses should have certain characteristics regarding their advocacy role. Thus, it is better to pay special attention to the training of these nurses in educational curricula. Since much time nurses spend much time on documentation (about 90%

in non-emergency departments and 70% in emergency departments based on data from the participants in this study), a sufficient opportunity should be given to them to fulfill their job responsibilities. Also, the use of a special group of nurses in an emergency can be effective for both them and their clients.

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